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Spending Habits and Daily Allowance Satisfaction of Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of spending habit of ABM students in terms of academic purpose, food allowance and personal needs, and to determine their daily allowance satisfaction. This study also aims to examine if there is a significant relationship between spending habit and daily allowance satisfaction. The researcher conducted a quantitative research study and used correlational and descriptive research design. This study used total population sampling as sampling technique as this used the forty-two (42) ABM students in Malalag Cogon National High School in the schoolyear 2024-2025. The researchers used mean and Spearman Rho as the statistical tools. The researchers conducted a pilot testing to test the reliability of the questionnaires and the results of the Cronbach's Alpha were good. Based on the findings, the level of spending habits of ABM students is moderate, and their level of daily allowance satisfaction is high. On the other hand, spending habits in terms of food, personal needs and academic purpose have a low positive correlation in the student's satisfaction in allowance for their personal needs, food and academic purpose. In addition, the researcher recommended that in order to minimize the expenses of the students, they should be responsible for the things they buy, prioritize their needs over wants, and know how to budget their daily allowance so that they can control their spending habits and avoid allowance dissatisfaction.

Keywords: *ABM, spending habit, daily allowance satisfaction, Philippines*

Introduction

Nowadays, the young generation spends more money on online shopping, convenience, travel, socializing, and online gaming than on homes and cars compared to previous generations. This bad habit affects spending behavior as the young generation tries to follow trends and buy anything they want without thinking twice. When this bad habit occurs, it will cause problems such as not being able to afford enough to pay for loans, rent, car loans, and more. Therefore, this problem needs to be focused on so that the younger generation, especially students, do not develop bad habits (Kumar, Sudin, Othman & Salehuddin, 2022).

Therefore, financial literacy becomes a more significant function in the economy's overall health as well as the financial security of each individual. Since 2000, the idea of financial literacy has evolved in five ways: (1) related to understanding financial concepts; (2) using those concepts to compute prices, such as the cost of goods and services; (3) managing personal finances; (4) ability to make wise financial decisions; and (5) confidence in successfully anticipating future financial needs. When considering financial services from the supply side (demand side), this confidence is also one of the elements influencing Vietnam's financial inclusion (Tran, 2022).

On the other hand, A study in the US claims that college students have a poor perception of money since they have little savings, spend carelessly, and have a lot of debt. The battle to pay for their education is something that many students face. According to more research, students' financial management is impacted by the decisions they make regarding money nowadays, which can lead to a variety of problems with graduating, finding work, and saving for retirement in addition to immediate health problems associated to stress. Comprehending these associations is crucial for efficiently preparing the upcoming generation for monetary prosperity (Widener, 2017).

On the other hand, the majority of students handle their own financial affairs and receive assistance from the National Higher Education Fund Corporation, scholarships, personal savings, or family funds. Numerous earlier research on students' finances have been done; some of these focus on students' awareness of managing their finances. Research has been done on student's expectations and practices around spending, as well as the connection between their average grade and their monthly allowance (Hassan & Wahid, 2023)

Also, it has been demonstrated that certain demographic data that affect students' financial support have no effect on satisfaction. This essentially means that a student's degree of happiness with financial support is unaffected by how well they handle their finances, including their attitude toward spending and the amount of their daily allowance. Nonetheless, a student who receives satisfactory financial support tends to be more self-assured, more tolerant, and less prone to stress, all of which enhance personal wellbeing (Villanueva & Suninguit, 2024).

So, a study is conducted to determine the correlation between their monthly stipend and their daily spending. The researchers used a form of quantitative survey research to collect data for this study at Universiti Teknologi Mara Jengka, Pahang (UCPh). There were 152 students from all different UCPh faculties who participated in this research. Using the Pearson correlation technique and the data collected by IBM SPSS Statistics 25 Software, it can be inferred that there is no statistically significant association between their daily spending and their monthly allowance (Hassan & Wahid, 2023).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine if there is a significant relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of spending habits in terms of spending for food, personal needs and academic purpose of ABM students?
2. What is the level of daily allowance satisfaction in terms of satisfaction for food allowance, personal needs and academic allowance of ABM students?
3. What is the significance relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction of ABM students?

Literature Review

Money plays a crucial role in life, especially for students living in distant cities. It presents a significant challenge as students are expected to be more prudent in financial management. Money, in essence, serves as a tool for conducting transactions involving the purchase of goods and services. The amount of pocket money a student receives significantly influences their buying behavior. Students use pocket money to purchase essentials such as food, beverages, clothing, and academic necessities like accommodation, transportation, and more. Typically, students receive pocket money on a weekly or monthly basis. However, pocket money also influences decisions regarding online shopping. It represents the funds received by an individual over a specific period. Pocket money can come from scholarships, parental support, or from students who work part-time (Rismayanti & Oktapiani, 2020; Armelia & Irianto, 2021).

Additionally, most of the students spent their money food, transportation, education and entertainment. The researchers concluded that most of the students received monthly allowances from their parents. They spent most of their allowances on food and transportation. It is normal since they live independently due to the location of the university or due to the requirement of the university itself (Hassan & Wahid, 2023).

Also, the concept of online shopping encompasses a procedural framework anticipated by consumers, serving the purpose of fulfilling their individual needs by procuring goods or services through digital trade channels tailored to their preferences. The transactional process of online shopping typically transpires via manufacturers or authorized distributors leveraging social media platforms, culminating in consumers effecting payment through digital means such as mobile banking or Cash on Delivery (COD). Subsequently, sellers coordinate logistical arrangements through courier services to deliver the purchased items to the designated address or recipient (Harahap, 2018).

Moreover, impulsive buying the negative impacts of online purchases also lead to consumptive behavior among students that is correlated with online buying and selling activities. Consumptive behavior is defined as an action by consumers to acquire an item that is not in line with their needs or demands; however, continuous acquisition of such items can result in wastefulness or inefficiency in financial costs. This consumptive behavior represents extravagance in consuming goods or services, thereby leading to wastefulness this consumptive behavior arises from a persistent desire that acts in accordance with a longing, driven by a strong desire that disregards the benefits of the goods or services acquired, yet this behavior provides satisfaction (Azizah & Aswad, 2022).

On the other hand, according to Falahati, Sabri, and Paim (2012), being able to control one's financial behavior is a requirement for success in life. Financial literacy is one of the most crucial measures of a person's financial satisfaction and spending habits. There is a significant relationship between financial management knowledge and the spending habits of university students. In summary, if the knowledge is provided, pupils are able to make sensible financial decisions. Financial planning is a method of preparing for personal or family financial needs in a more efficient manner. It is crucial for individuals to have an awareness of the importance of financial planning, whether in simple or complex forms, once they have chosen their own resources (Altfest, 2004; Kamis, Samad, Pheng, Rasli, Hajali & Peing, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers conducted a quantitative research study and used correlational and descriptive research design. Quantitative research is a form of research that relies on the methods of natural sciences, which produces numerical data and hard facts. It aims at establishing cause and effect relationship between two variables by using mathematical, computational and statistical methods. Descriptive correlation design can provide an overview of the current situation. Psychology, for example, can represent a specific group of people, their perspectives, behaviors, or feelings. A correlational research design investigates the relationship or correlation between variables without the researcher intentionally influencing or controlling any of the variables (Bhandari, 2021; Ahmad, Wasim, Irfan, Gogoi, Srivastava, & Farheen, 2019; IvyPanda, 2022).

A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. The direction and/or degree of the relationship between two or more variables are reflected in a correlation. A connection may have a positive or negative direction. A non-experimental research approach called correlational research uses statistical analysis to examine the relationship between two variables. The impacts of unrelated factors on the variables being studied are not examined by

correlational research designs. Correlational research can be utilized to ascertain the link between two variables in situations when conducting experimental research is unethical (Devi, Barkha & Lepcha, Mrs & Basnet; Shakeela, 2023).

Respondents

The study used total population sampling in distributing survey questionnaires for Grade 11 and 12 ABM learners. The respondents encountered different questions and giving feedbacks about the study. The survey that they used was adopted and modified. It has undergone validation of three expert validators and have undergone pilot testing. The researchers used Cronbach's alpha to determine the reliability of the questionnaires.

Since ABM strand was focus of the study, the respondents are only the ABM learners. Researchers used total population sampling in choosing respondents which was good in obtaining result from the survey.

Table 1. The Respondents

Grade level	Male	Female	Total
11 ABM	7	20	27
12 ABM	3	12	15
Total	12	35	42

Instrument

This quantitative researcher used survey questionnaires that are used to gather data about Spending habits and Daily Allowance Satisfaction of ABM students of Malalag Cogon National High School. The questionnaires were constructed based on the research objectives. It consists of three (3) part. The first part consists of fifteen (15) questions that all about spending habits: five (5) questions for spending for food, another five (5) for spending for personal needs and five (5) for spending academic purpose. The second part is about their school allowance that they received from their parents/guardians every day. However, the third part consists of fifteen (15) questions that all about of their daily allowance satisfaction: five (5) question for satisfaction for food allowance, another five (5) for satisfaction of personal needs, and five (5) for satisfaction for academic allowance. The respondents answered these questionnaires through the likert scale adopt on this study (Elevazo, Biason, Rosa, Embante, Fernandez, Orcajada & Decena, 2023).

In order to gather data, the researchers looked for details that are related to the researchers' study. The researchers gathered data by survey questionnaire in order to collected the data in a standardized way so that the data are internally consistent and coherent for analysis. A questionnaire is used in case resources are limited as a questionnaire can be quite inexpensive to design and administer and time is an important resource which a questionnaire consumes to its maximum extent, protection of the privacy of the participants as participants will respond honestly only if their identity is hidden and confidentiality is maintained, and corroborating with other findings as questionnaires can be useful confirmation tools when corroborated with other studies that have resources to pursue other data collection strategies (Roopa & Rani, 2012).

The survey instrument was a self-administrated questionnaire, developed through adaptation and adoption. According to Sebastian, Gunnar, and Gunter (2007), adopting individual questions from established questionnaires is an effective and efficient measuring instrument in view that the questionnaires had a good stability, sensitivity, reliability and validity. However, a modification or adaptation of different items might be necessary in order to improve the credibility of the research findings (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2003).

Procedure

This step ensured that the study aligns with the school's policies and educational goals. The principal's approval also signifies that the research is considered ethical and appropriate for the student population. This approval process may involve presenting a research proposal outlining the study's objectives, methods, and potential benefits to the students and the school. Additionally, the principal may provide guidance on how to carry out the study in a way that minimizes disruptions to regular school activities. Gaining approval also means the researchers can access necessary resources, such as student lists or survey distribution channels.

By giving their consent, students guarantee that they are aware of the study's objectives, methods, and possible hazards and voluntarily engage in it. Giving students clear and understandable access to comprehensive study information is a necessary step in the consent process. The purpose of the study, the kinds of data that will be gathered, the way in which the data will be utilized, and the participants' rights—such as the freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without incurring fees—should all be included in this material.

This entails figuring out which individual ABM students meet the study's requirements, like those who fall into a given age range, year level, or academic standing. In order to gather the students, it may be necessary to work with the teachers to arrange meetings at times that won't interfere too much with their academic obligations. Researchers used paper-pencil questionnaires during the data gathering. Researcher also ensure that the survey is designed to be user friendly, with questions that are easy to understand and answer.

Data Analysis

This study used Spearman Rho and weight mean as the statistical tools. It is typically denoted either with the Greek letter rho (ρ), or

rs. Like all correlation coefficients, Spearman's rho measures the strength of association between two variables. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is similar to the Pearson correlation coefficient (Jia, Yang, Zheng, Zhu & Bi, 2020).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the findings of the study. The first part describes the level of spending habits of Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) students, and the second part is their daily allowance satisfaction. Lastly, the third part present the relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction of ABM students.

School Allowance of ABM Students

Table 2. *School Allowance*

<i>Ranges of School Allowance</i>	<i>Frequency of Students</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
10 – 20 pesos	6	14.29%
21 – 30 pesos	9	21.43%
31 – 40 pesos	2	4.76%
41 - 50 pesos	14	33.33%
51 – 60 pesos	8	19.05%
61 – 70 pesos	3	7.14%
71 – 80 pesos	0	0%
81 – 90 pesos	0	0%
91 and above pesos	0	0%
Total	42	100%

This tally shows the number of frequency of students in each range of school allowances. The range of school allowance with the highest frequency are 41 – 50 (33.33%) pesos followed by 21 – 30 pesos (21.43%), 51 – 60 pesos (19.05%) and 10 – 20 pesos (14.29%). While the ranges of school allowance with the lowest frequency are 91 and above pesos (0%), 81 – 90 pesos (0%), 71 – 80 pesos (0%) followed by 31 – 40 pesos (4.76%) and 61 – 70 pesos (7.14%). Allowances refers to an amount of money given by the parents or guardians in a certain time period to support students' financial needs.

Table 3. *Level of Students Spending Habit*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Spending for Food	3.71	Agree	High
2. Spending for Personal Needs	3.55	Agree	High
3. Spending for Academic Purpose	3.15	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Overall	3.29	Moderately Agree	Moderate

Shown in table 3 is the level of spending habits of ABM students with the following indicators: spending for food allowance, spending for personal needs, and spending for academic purpose. The three indicators generated an overall mean of 3.29 which can be interpreted as moderate. This means that the ABM students moderately agree with their spending habits in the different indicators. Among the three indicators, food got the highest mean of 3.71 which is interpreted as high. This means that the ABM students agree that they are spending for food. On the other hand, personal needs obtained a mean of 3.55 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the ABM students agree that they are spending for personal needs. Lastly, academic purpose attained a mean of 3.15 which can be interpreted as moderate. This means that ABM students moderately agree that they are spending for academic purposes.

The results implies that the level of spending habits of ABM students in Malagal Cogon National High School is moderate. This indicates that the ABM students are spending in terms food, personal needs and academic purposes. However, the indicator with the highest mean was food which means that the ABM students agree that they are highly spending for food from their daily allowance. The indicators with the lowest mean were academic purposes. It means that the ABM students moderately agree that they are spending in terms of academic purposes.

The result of this study supports the findings Mandell and Klein (2019) and Wagland and Taylor (2019) that early financial management education often results in bad financial habits. Young individuals are frequently impacted by financial difficulties. Due to their lack of financial literacy, children are compelled to make difficult financial decisions at an early age, especially when they are just starting their careers. In the end, they made a poor decision that severely affected their lives. To achieve economic well-being, people must be financially educated to recognize and distinguish between various providers, products, and services.

Daily Allowances Satisfaction of ABM students

Table 4 showed the level of daily allowance satisfaction of ABM students with the following indicators: satisfaction for food allowance, satisfaction for personal needs, and satisfaction for academic allowance. The indicators generated an overall mean of 3.82 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied of their daily allowance.

However, satisfaction of food allowance got highest mean of 4.05 which is interpreted as high. This means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their food allowance. In addition, satisfaction of personal needs obtained a mean of 3.91 which can

be interpreted as high. This means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their daily allowance for personal needs. Lastly, satisfaction of academic allowance attained a mean of 3.5 which can be interpreted as high. Thus, this means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their daily allowance for academic purposes.

Table 4. *Daily Allowance Satisfaction*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Satisfaction for Food Allowance	4.05	Agree	High
2.	Satisfaction for Personal Needs Allowances	3.91	Agree	High
3.	Satisfaction for Academic Allowance	3.5	Agree	High
	Overall	3.82	Agree	High

The result implied that the level of daily allowance satisfaction among ABM students in Malagal Cogon National High School is high. This indicates that the ABM students are indeed satisfied with their daily allowance. However, the indicators with the highest mean were satisfaction of food allowance which means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their daily allowance in terms of food. The indicator with the lowest mean was impact. It also means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their daily allowance in terms of academic purposes.

The results of this study support the findings Moneva et al., (2020) which showed that the students' level of financial support satisfaction towards their daily allowances is to ascertain the relationship between the students' daily allowance and their degree of financial support satisfaction. The number of students' daily allowance determines how satisfied they are with their financial support. A student who effectively manages their finances has less obligations and debts, which tends to raise their degree of financial support satisfaction.

Additionally, a student who is content with their financial aid is more self-assured, more tolerant, and less likely to experience stress, all of which contribute to their enhanced personal wellbeing. To improve budgeting abilities and raise financial support satisfaction, this study recommends more research on students who incur debt at a young age.

Significant Relationship Between Spending Habit and Daily Allowance Satisfaction

Table 5 represents the significant relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction. As shown in the table, all the indicators of spending habits are positively correlated with the indicators of daily allowance satisfaction since the p- value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5. *Significant relationship between spending habit and daily allowance Satisfaction*

<i>Daily Allowance Satisfaction</i>	<i>Spending Habits</i>		
	<i>Spending for Food</i>	<i>Spending for Personal Needs</i>	<i>Spending for Academic Purpose</i>
Satisfaction for Food Allowance	*0.3226 (0.0372)	*0.4462 (0.0031)	*0.5158 (0.0005)
Satisfaction for Personal Needs	*0.3168 (0.0409)	*0.3510 (0.0227)	*0.3226 (0.0372)
Satisfaction for Academic Purpose	*0.3246 (0.036)	*0.3169 (0.0409)	*0.5535 (0.0001)

These findings show the relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction of learners particularly focusing on ABM students. This was supported by the study of Moneva et al., (2020). As this study showed that there is a significant relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction, even though the satisfaction is not really affected to the learners. The higher their daily allowance, the more satisfied they could be. In addition, the study has a good impact or support the relationship between spending habits and daily allowance satisfaction.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were made;

The level of daily allowance satisfaction is high in terms of satisfaction of food allowance, which means that the ABM students agree that they are satisfied with their daily allowance in terms of food.

The level of spending habits of the learners is high in terms of food, because it was mentioned that the ABM students agree that they are highly spending for food from their daily allowance.

There is a significant relationship between daily allowance satisfaction and spending habits. It is stated that every indicator was significantly related as it shows that the higher their daily allowance, the more satisfied they could be.

References

Ahmad, S., Wasim, S., Irfan, S., Gogoi, S., Srivastava, A., & Farheen, Z. (2019). Qualitative v/s. quantitative research-a summarized review. *population*, 1(2), 2828-2832.

- Alfest, L. (2004). Personal financial planning: Origins, developments and a plan for future direction. *The American Economist*, 48(2), 53–60.
- Armelia, Y., & Irianto, A. (2021). Pengaruh Uang Saku Dan Gaya Hidup Terhadap Perilaku Konsumtif Mahasiswa. *EcoGen*, 4(3).
- Azizah, M., & Aswad, M. (2022). Pengaruh Belanja Online Pada E-Commerce Shopee Terhadap Perilaku Konsumtif Generasi Millennial di Blitar. *Jurnal Cendekia Ilmiah*, 1(4).
- Bhandari, P. (2021, July 7) An Introduction to Correlational Research.
- Elevazo, R., Biason, C. A. G., Rosa, C. D. D., Embate, J. D., Fernandez, A. C., Orcajada, H. M. O. & Decena III, J. T. (2023). Self-Esteem and Study Habits Among Accountancy, Business and Management Students of Tacurong National High School.
- Harahap, D. A. (2018). Perilaku Belanja Online di Indonesia. *JRMSI-Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Indonesia*, 9(2), 193–213.
- Hassan, N. N. A., & Wahid, N. A. A. (2023). Relationship Between the Monthly Allowance and Daily Expenses Among UiTM Jengka Students. *Randwick International of Social Science Journal*, 4(4), 785-794.
- IvyPanda. (2022, November 5). Data Presentation: Descriptive and Correlational Designs
- Kumar, D. S., Sudin, H., Othman, J., & Salehuddin, S. (2022). The influence of spending behaviour among university students in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 4(3), 30-43.
- Mandell, L., & Klein, L. (2009). The impact of financial literacy education on subsequent financial behavior. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning*, 20(1), 16-22.
- Moneva, J., & Tuñacao, M. (2020). Students' level of financial support satisfaction towards their daily allowance. *IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2455-2526.
- Rismayanti, T., & Oktapiani, S. (2020). The Influence of Pocket Money and Lifestyle on Consumptive Behavior of Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business. *Nusantara Journal Of Economics (NJE)*, 2(2), 31–37.
- Roopa, S., & Rani, M. S. (2012). Questionnaire designing for a survey. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*, 46(4_suppl1), 273-277.
- Saunders, M, Lewis P., & Thornhill, A. (2003). "Research Methods for Business Students". 3rd Edition, Harlow, Pearson Education.
- Sebastian Schulz, Gunnar Mau, and Gunter Siberer. 2007. "The Catalog Usability Questionnaire Adoption and Validation of a Usability Scale for Print-Catalogs". *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods* 5(2), 93-104
- Tran, T. V. (2022). Impact of Financial Literacy on Vietnamese Students' Spending Management. *VNU Journal of Economics and Business*, 2(4).
- Villanueva, Japeth & Suminguit, Marymae. (2024). STUDENTS PERCEIVED PURCHASING INTENSIONS TOWARD COUNTERFEIT CLOTHING.
- Wagland, S. P., & Taylor, S. (2009). When it comes to financial literacy, is sex really an issue? *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 3(1), 3-6.
- Widener, K. (2017). Financial management issues of college-aged students: Influences and consequences. <https://firescholars.seu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1063&context=honors>

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